

The prevalence and demographic pattern of obesity and its correlates in undergraduates of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike south-east, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the prevalence and demographic pattern of obesity and its correlates in undergraduates of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike, south-east Nigeria, using standard methods in a total of 200 {99 (49.5%) males and 101 (50.5%) females} randomly selected subjects. With obesity cut-off of $>27 \text{ kg/m}^2$, 22% of the total subjects were obese, representing 9.5% and 12.5% of the male and female, respectively relative to total subject, but 9.19 % and 24.75 % in the males and females relative to total by sex. The highest prevalence was in the 21-23 age group (total = 50.00 %; male = 52.63 % and female = 48.00 %). Based on the body mass index (BMI) cut-off, higher males (94.74%) than females (88.0%) were overweight whereas based on the total body fat (TBF) class, higher females (17, 68.0%) than males (10, 52.63%) were obese. Based on waist to hip ratio (WHPR) all females (but no male) were in the lower risk class. However, high proportion of either sex was in the desired/normal class based on systolic blood pressure (SBP) (Total = 59.09%, female =56.00%; male =.63.16%), diastolic blood pressure (DBP) (Total = 68.18%; female = 68.0%; male = 68.42%) and blood glucose level (BGL) Total =65.90%; female = 76.00%; male = 52.63%). Thus, the obesity prevalence was higher in the females and highest in the 21-23 age group indicating apparent risk of developing obesity-related diseases particularly in the females and 21-23 age group of the studied population.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Obesity may result to (and is characterized by) excessive accumulation of fat, hence is generally defined by an excess of body fat [1] or a body mass index (BMI) of 30 kg/m^2 or higher. However, overweight, generally described as a body mass index (BMI) of 25 to 30 kg/m^2 , could imply obese since the obese are in principle overweight. To disambiguate the two terms, it is better to use the term pre-obese when overweight but not obese is implied or to use the clarification of BMI categories as proposed by World Health Organization [2]. The prevalence of overweight and obesity varies considerably between countries and even regions within countries [3] and confer elevated health risks, including cardiovascular diseases [1,4,5].

In particular, the pathogenesis of obesity is multifaceted and was associated with a complex interplay of genetic factors, lifestyle and environment [6,7]. Obesity in concert with hypertension and type 2 diabetes mellitus constitutes metabolic syndrome that could predispose one to further health challenges [8,9,10,4,11,12]. Generally, overweight and, concomitantly, obesity are common nutritional problem among youth in many countries, including Nigeria. Overweight and obesity are variously classified [13; 2] essentially based on varied cut-off of their correlates, including body mass index (BMI), total body fat (TBF) and waist to hip ratio (WHPR).

Thus, this study determined the prevalence and demographic pattern of obesity and its

correlates in male and female undergraduates in Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike, Nigeria. To achieve the stated aim, the study assessed the respondents'/students' height and weight to calculate BMI, and measured their total body fat, blood pressure (diastolic and systolic) and blood glucose level, using standard instruments. Assessing other correlates of obesity along with BMI is of higher prognostic value than assessing BMI alone [14].

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Subject

Cross sectional random convenience sampling was performed among undergraduates in Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, a major Federal higher institution of learning very close to the Umuahia, the capital of Abia state, south-east Nigeria. The study was carried out between June and August, 2014 as a group degree project. An overview of this study was related to the subjects who were apparently healthy and unrelated university students, and of fairly diverse ethnic groups within Nigeria. The Board of Department of Biochemistry, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike approved this study in accordance with the Helsinki declaration, and every subject gave oral informed consent.

2.2 Questionnaire and anthropometric measurement

A structured and validated questionnaire (Nutritional Status and Lifestyle Questionnaire - A guide for personal assessment of RenaiSante Institute of Integrative Medicine) was issued out on informed consents to the study population to evaluate their demographic (age and sex) data and to exclude subjects with health issues, including family history for any genetic diseases, on health threatening habit, including tobacco smoking and alcohol intake. Thus, two hundred (200) (males = 99; females = 101) asymptomatic students, aged seventeen to twenty-eight (17-28) were randomly selected for this study.

Anthropometric parameters, including weight, height, waist and hip circumference, were measured and the relevant ones used for computing BMI and waist to hip ratio (WHPR). Total body fat, blood glucose level, systolic and diastolic blood pressure were assessed in the so determined obese subjects, using standard measurements, calculations and protocols.

In brief, respective participants height was measured using a height meter or Stadiometer () with individual participant, wearing light clothing and no shoes, and standing in the middle of the scale, and without touching anything. The height in cm, waist and hip circumference in inch of the subjects were measured using measuring tape and their WHPR

was calculated accordingly. The waist circumference and hip circumference were measured at the level of the umbilicus, using an inelastic tape measure and the waist to hip ratio (WHPR) calculated from the two values and categorized according to the World Health Organization criteria ([2]WHO, 2000).

Total Body Fat was accordingly calculated using the Body Fat Mass Calculator or Monitor (BEURER Digital Weight and Body Fat Mass Calculator, Model BG 51XXL, Germany). A bio-impedance weight and body fat weighing scale (BEURER Digital Weight and Body Fat Mass Calculator, Model BG 51XXL, Germany) was used to determine the weight and Total Body Fat while the BMI was calculated from the corresponding measurements, using the relation:

$$BMI = \frac{Mass (kg)}{x^2}$$

where x is equal to height in meters (m)

2.3 Classification basis

From the calculated BMI, normal weight, overweight, and obesity were determined using the World Health Organization (WHO) criteria for body weight classification [2]. Weight status was categorized into four; Underweight ($BMI < 18.5 \text{ kg/m}^2$), Normal weight (Between 18.5 kg/m^2 and 24.99 kg/m^2), Overweight (BMI between 25.0 kg/m^2 and 29.99 kg/m^2) and Obese ($BMI > 30 \text{ kg/m}^2$, according to WHO [2].

The waist circumference to hip ratio (WHPR) measurement was classified into low risk, moderate risk and high risk, according to WHO [2] thus:

Class	women	men
Low risk	< 0.95	< 0.80
Moderate risk	0.96-1.0	0.81-0.85
High risk	> 1.0	> 0.85

Subjects with BMI cut-off of $\geq 27 \text{ kg m}^{-2}$ were considered obese according to Yap, et al. [13], and used to determine the prevalence of obesity and non-obesity among the subjects. The thus selected obese subjects were further classified by other cut-offs, including BMI, and TBF.

2.4 Statistical analysis

The subjects responses were coded, calculated and analyzed using IBM SPSS (statistical package for social sciences) statistics version 20. Frequency distribution means and percentages were computed. Cross tabulation was used to compare two variables. The analysis of data obtained was carried out using SPSS for Windows version 16.0 (SPSS, Chicago, IL) and the results, presented as Means \pm SD for sample size, n = recorded respective number of cases. Test of significance was not carried out.

3. RESULTS

None reported any health history, including vascular conditions, cancer, gastrointestinal tract problem or (for the female) case of pregnancy, breast feeding and fibrocystic disease. None reported any non-diet related habit, including smoking or family history for any form of cancer. None reported any case of stress, intake of nutritional supplements, incidence of allergies or on medication. None have had surgeries or any conditions/disabilities not covered/mentioned in the questionnaire.

As shown in Table 1, out of the two hundred respondents, 99 representing 49.5 % were male while 101 representing 50.5 % were female. The recorded obesity (cut-off point as in the design) in the total studied subjects was 44 (made up of 19 and 25 respectively in the male and female subjects) while the non-obese in the total subjects was 156 (Male = 80 while Female = 76). This represented obesity prevalence of 22% in the total subjects while 9.5% and 12.5% respectively in the male and female subjects relative to the total subjects but 19.19% and 24.75% respectively in and relative to the male and female subjects. The recorded 22 % obesity prevalence among the students was slightly higher in the females (12.5%) than in the males (9.5%).

Obesity case was highest in the 21-23 age group for the Total (22), male (10) and female (12) subjects while the prevalence in the total, male and female subjects for the age group was 50.00 %, 52.63 % and 48.00 %, respectively (Table 2.). The distribution of the obese subjects based on the BMI classification and sex is presented in Table 3 with the highest proportion of the obese in the overweight class than in the Type 1 obesity class for the male (18

representing prevalent rate of 9.00 % in the total subjects and 94.74 % in the male subject) and for the female (22 representing 11.00 % for total subjects and 88.00 % for the female subjects). More female than male subjects were in the overweight (22) and Type 1 obesity (3) class compared to male subjects in the overweight (18) and Type 1 obesity (1) class, but the prevalence for obese and overweight was higher in the male (94.74%) than in the female (88.0%) whereas the prevalence for obese and Type 1 obesity was higher in the female (12.0%) than in the male (5.26%).

As shown in Table 4, the highest proportion of the obese based on the TBF class (17, 68.0%) followed by 10, 52.63% were recorded among the females and males respectively and in the obese class. None of the female obese was in the athlete class. Table 5 showed that all the female obese were in the lower risk class compared to only one for the male obese while 9 representing 47.37% each of the male obese was in the moderate and high risk class. However, high proportion of obese students (of either sex) was in the desired SBP class followed by pre-hypertension class while the proportion of obese students in stage1 hypertension and stage 2 hypertension was very low and in the females (Table 6).

Based on the DBP class, high proportion of the obese subjects was in the desired class followed by the pre-hypertension class whereas low proportion of the obese male was in the stage 1 hypertension class while low proportion of the obese female was in the stage 2 hypertension class (Table 7). High proportion of the obese subjects was in the normal class followed by the hypoglycemia class. However, 21.05% of the male but none of the female obese was in the hyperglycemia class (Table 8).

Table 1. Prevalence and pattern of obesity and non obesity in the subjects according to sex

Sex	Total by sex		Non obese (Prevalence%)		Obese (Prevalence%)	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Male	99	49.5	80	40.0 (80.81)	19	9.5 (19.19)
Female	101	50.5	76	38.0 (75.25)	25	12.5 (24.75)
Total	200	100	156	78	44	22

N/B: % calculated based on the Total (Male and Female) subjects. Values in bracket represent percentage based on total by sex.

Table 2. Prevalence and pattern of obesity and non obesity in the male and female subjects according to age group

Sex	Age group	Total by age group		Obese but in other age group (Prevalence relative to total by sex %)		Obese (Prevalence relative to total by sex %)	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
Male	18 – 20	28	14.00 (28.20)	15	7.5 (78.95)	4	2.0 (21.05)
	21 – 23	41	20.50 (41.40)	9	4.5 (47.37)	10	5.0 (52.63)
	≥ 24	30	15.00 (30.30)	14	7.0 (73.68)	5	2.5 (26.32)
Female	18 – 20	22	11.00 (21.98)	17	8.5 (68.00)	8	4.0 (32.00)
	21 – 23	44	22.00 (43.56)	13	6.5 (52.00)	12	6.0 (48.00)
	≥ 24	35	17.50 (34.65)	20	10 (80.00)	5	2.5 (20.00)
Total(Male+Female)	18 – 20	50	25.00	32	18 (72.73)	12	6.0 (27.27)
	21 – 23	85	42.50	22	11 (50.00)	22	11.0 (50.00)
	≥ 24	65	32.50	34	17 (77.28)	10	5.0 (22.72)

N/B: % calculated based on the Total (Male and Female) subjects. Value in bracket calculated based on the total obese by either sex alone or combined accordingly

Table 3. Distribution of the obese subjects based on the BMI classification and sex

Sex	BMI class		Overweight		Total	
	Type 1 obesity No	%	No	%	No	%
Male	1	0.50 (5.26)	18	9.00 (94.74)	19	9.50 (100)
Female	3	1.50 (12.0)	22	11.00 (88.00)	25	12.50 (100)
Total	4	2.00 (9.09)	40	20.00 (90.91)	44	22.00 (100)

N/B: % calculated based on the Total (Male and Female) subjects. Value in bracket calculated based on the total obese by either sex alone or combined accordingly

Table 4. Distribution of obese subjects based on the Total Body Fat, TBF class and sex

TBF class	Sex	Obese but in a different TBF class		Obese		Total	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
Athlete	Male	14	7.00 (73.68)	5	2.50 (26.32)	19	9.50 (100)
	Female	25	12.50 (100)	0	0.00 (0.00)	25	12.50 (100)
	Total	39	19.5 (88.64)	5	2.50 (13.36)	44	22.00 (100)
Fitness	Male	18	9.00 (94.74)	1	0.50 (5.26)	19	9.50 (100)
	Female	24	12.00 (96.00)	1	0.50 (4.0)	25	12.50 (100)
	Total	42	21.00 (95.45)	2	1.00 (4.55)	44	22.00 (100)
Acceptable	Male	16	8.00 (84.21)	3	1.50 (15.79)	19	9.50 (100)
	Female	18	9.00 (72.00)	7	3.50 (28.00)	25	12.50 (100)
	Total	34	17.00 (77.27)	10	5.00 (22.73)	44	22.00 (100)
Obese	Male	9	4.50 (47.37)	10	5.00 (52.63)	19	9.50 (100)
	Female	8	4.00 (32.00)	17	8.50 (68.00)	25	12.50 (100)
	Total	17	8.50 (36.64)	27	13.50 (61.36)	44	22.00 (100)

N/B: % calculated based on the Total (Male and Female) subjects. Value in bracket calculated based on the total obese by either sex alone or combined accordingly

Table 5. The distribution of the obese subjects based on the WHPR class and sex

WHPR class	Sex	Obese but in a different WHPR		Obese		Total	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
Lower risk	Male	18	9.0(94.74)	1	0.5 (5.26)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	0	0.0(0.00)	25	12.5 (100)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	18	9.0(40.91)	26	13.0(59.09)	44	22(100)
Moderate risk	Male	10	5.0(52.63)	9	4.5(47.37)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	25	12.5(100)	0	0.00(0.00)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	35	17.5(79.55)	9	4.5(20.45)	44	22(100)
High risk	Male	10	52.63	9	4.5(47.37)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	25	12.5(100)	0	0.00(0.00)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	35	17.5(79.55)	9	4.5(20.45)	44	22(100)

N/B: % calculated based on the Total (Male and Female) subjects. Value in bracket calculated based on the total obese by either sex alone or combined accordingly

Table 6. The distribution of the obese subjects based on the SBP class and sex

SBP class	Sex	Obese but in a different SBP class		Obese		Total	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
Desired	Male	7	3.5(36.84)	12	6.0(63.16)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	11	5.5(44.00)	14	7.0(56.00)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	18	9.0(40.91)	26	13.0(59.09)	44	22.0(100)
Pre-hypertension	Male	12	6.0(63.16)	7	3.5(36.84)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	16	8.0(64.00)	9	4.5(36.00)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	28	14.0(63.64)	16	8.0(36.36)	44	22.0(100)
Stage 1 Hypertension	Male	19	9.5(100)	0	0.0(0.00)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	24	12.0(96.00)	1	0.5(4.00)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	43	21.5(97.73)	1	0.5(2.27)	44	22.0(100)
Stage 2 Hypertension	Male	19	9.5(100)	0	0.0(0.00)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	24	12.0(96.00)	1	0.5(4.00)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	43	21.5(97.73)	1	0.5(2.27)	44	22.0(100)

N/B: % calculated based on the Total (Male and Female) subjects. Value in bracket calculated based on the total obese by either sex alone or combined accordingly

Table 7. Prevalence rate or distribution of obesity in the subjects based on the DBP class and sex

DBP class	Sex	Obese but in a different DBP class		Obese		Total	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
Hypotension	Male	18	9.0(94.74)	1	0.5(5.26)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	22	11.0(88.0)	3	1.5(12.0)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	40	20.0(90.91)	4	2(9.09)	44	22.0(100)
Desired	Male	6	3(31.58)	13	6.5(68.42)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	8	4(32.0)	17	8.5(68.0)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	14	7(31.82)	30	15.0(68.18)	44	22.0(100)
Pre-hypertension	Male	14	7(73.68)	5	2.5(26.32)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	21	10.5(84.0)	4	2.0(16.0)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	35	17.5(79.55)	9	4.5(20.45)	44	22.0(100)
Stage 1 Hypertension	Male	17	8.5(89.47)	2	1.0(10.53)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	25	12.5(100)	0	0.0(0.0)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	42	21(95.45)	2	1.0(4.55)	44	22.0(100)
Stage 2 Hypertension	Male	19	9.5(100)	0	0.0(0.0)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	24	12.0(96.0)	1	0.5(4.0)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	43	21.5(97.73)	1	0.5(2.27)	44	22.0(100)

N/B: % calculated based on the Total (Male and Female) subjects. Value in bracket calculated based on the total obese by either sex alone or combined accordingly

Table 8: Prevalence rate or distribution of obesity in the subjects abased on the Blood glucose level class and sex

Blood glucose level class	Sex	Obese but in a different Blood glucose level class		Obese		Total	
		No	%	No	%	No	%
Hypoglycemia	Male	14	7.0(73.69)	5	2.5(26.31)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	19	9.5(76.0)	6	3.0(24.0)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	33	16.5(75.0)	11	5.5(25.0)	44	22.0(100)
Normal	Male	9	4.5(47.37)	10	5.0(52.63)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	6	3.0(24.0)	19	9.5(76.00)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	15	7.5(34.10)	29	14.5(65.90)	44	22.0(100)
Hyperglycemia	Male	15	7.5(78.95)	4	2.0(21.05)	19	9.5(100)
	Female	25	12.5(100)	0	0.0(0.00)	25	12.5(100)
	Total	40	20.0(90.91)	4	2.0(9.09)	44	22.0(100)

N/B: % calculated based on the Total (Male and Female) subjects. Value in bracket calculated based on the total obese by either sex alone or combined accordingly

4. DISCUSSION

The study investigated overweight and obesity prevalence, pattern and correlates in undergraduates of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike, south-east Nigeria, using cross sectional random convenience sampling and relevant standard protocols. None reported any health history, including vascular conditions, cancer, gastrointestinal tract problem or (for the female) case of pregnancy, breast feeding and fibrocystic disease. None reported any non-diet related habit, including smoking or family history for any form of cancer. None reported any case of stress, intake of nutritional supplements, incidence of allergies or on medication. None have had surgeries or any conditions/disabilities not covered/mentioned in the questionnaire.

Based on obesity cut-off of >27 , 22% of the total subjects were obese, representing 9.5% and 12.5% respectively in the male and female relative to total subject, but 9.19 % and 24.75 % in the males and females relative to total by sex while the highest prevalence was in the 21-23 age group (total = 50.00 %; male = 52.63 % and female = 48.00 %). The result compares with 22.2% obesity prevalence reported by Amira et al. [15] but is not up to one third of the studied population reported by Bakari et al. [16]. Thus, obesity prevalence is higher in the females compared to their male counterpart in line with Thiam et al. [17] that showed a greater percentage of obese women than men in Africa.

Obesity prevalence was highest in the 21-23 age group (total = 50.00 %; male = 52.63 % and female = 48.00 %), suggesting the vulnerability of this age group to incident overweight and obesity. The observation however contradicted the notion that overweight increases with age [3]. This could be attributed to the higher number of 21-23 age group (85) in the studied subjects compared to that of the ≥ 24 (65) which may skew the result.

Out of thus selected obese subjects but based on the body mass index (BMI) cut-off, higher males (94.74%) were in overweight class than

females (88.0%) whereas based on the total body fat (TBF) class, higher females (17, 68.0%) than males (10, 52.63%) were obese. The result indicate that higher male than female were overweight but not obese in support of the present result of this study on TBF-based classification of obesity and that of earlier reports [7,17,3] that overweight is more common or higher among men than among women while obesity is more common or higher among women. Similarly, based on waist to hip ratio (WHPR) all females (but no male) were in the lower risk class.

However, high proportion of either sex was in the desired/normal class based on systolic blood pressure (SBP) (Total = 59.09%, female =56.00%; male =.63.16%), diastolic blood pressure (DBP) (Total = 68.18%; female = 68.0%; male = 68.42%) and blood glucose level (BGL) Total =65.90%; female = 76.00%; male = 52.63%), suggesting that these obesity correlates may not be effective determinants of overweight and obesity in the studied population.

5. CONCLUSION

Thus, the obesity prevalence was higher in the females and highest in the 21-23 age group indicating apparent risk of developing obesity-related diseases particularly in the females and 21-23 age group of the studied population. The obesity prevalence among the subjects may fairly correlate with BMI and TBF, but not SBP, DBP and BGL, of the subjects. Test of significance was not carried out, which may limit the reliability of this study result, hence need to be addressed in similar further studies.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

ACCE designed the study, wrote the protocol, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. ONCE managed the analyses of the study. 'NA, ZIU, UOU and AGE managed the literature searches carried out the field study. All authors read and approved the final manuscript."

ETHICAL APPROVAL

All authors hereby declare that all experiments have been examined and approved by the appropriate ethics committee and have therefore been performed in accordance with the ethical standards laid down in the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki.

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